

Synthesis of (2*R*, 3*S*)-3-(*N,N*-dibenzylamino)-1-thiophenylbutan-2-ol†

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Synthesis of 3-mercapto-1,2-amino alcohols via S-H insertion reaction of an enantiopure *N,N*-dibenzyl- α -aminodiazoketones followed by a *syn*-selective borohydride reduction is described.

Enantiopure 1,2-amino alcohols (**1**) are important chiral auxiliaries that have found widespread use in a variety of asymmetric reactions¹. In particular, 1,2-amino alcohol mediated asymmetric addition of Et₂Zn to prochiral aldehydes has been widely studied, with up to 99% ee's being reported in some cases². Recently, enantiopure 1,2-aminothiols **2** have emerged as a new class of chiral auxiliaries for Et₂Zn additions to prochiral aldehydes³. Ongoing studies show that these aminothiols are equally promising mediators for asymmetric addition of Et₂Zn to aldehydes. We envisaged that 3-mercapto-1,2-amino alcohols (**3**), while representing an appropriate hybrid of the above two classes, would provide a new-generation of chiral auxiliaries having an additional coordination site for the organometallic species. We now present a concise synthetic route towards a representative 3-mercapto-1,2-amino alcohol derivative.

Among the various methods that are currently available for the stereoselective synthesis of 1,2-amino alcohols, hydride reductions of *N,N*-dibenzyl- α -amino ketones (Reetz-protocol)⁴ is a versatile method which produces *syn*-1,2-amino alcohols (Felkin product) with uniformly high diastereoselectivities ($\geq 90\%$ de's). This Reetz-protocol formed the cornerstone of our strategy towards the synthesis of enantiopure 3-mercapto-1,2-amino alcohol.

In the event, we started with *N,N*-dibenzyl-L-alanine **4**⁵ which was converted to the corresponding α -diazoketone **5** (64%) via the mixed anhydride method (Scheme 1). Rh-catalyzed intermolecular S-H insertion reaction⁶ to **5** with thiophenol then smoothly produced the *N,N*-dibenzyl- α -amino- α' -thiophenyl ketone **6** in 70% yield. The latter was subsequently reduced with NaBH₄ in MeOH at -20° to give the *syn*-3-phenylthio-1,2-amino alcohol **7** in 60% yield ($\geq 90\%$ de). The *syn*-stereochemistry in **7** was clearly evident from the high *J*-value (9.4 Hz) between the amino alcohol protons (H₂ and H₃) and is the one predicted by the Felkin model and as per Reetz's observations on similar reductions⁴. Asymmetric additions of Et₂Zn to aldehydes, mediated by **7**, is currently under investigation.

Scheme 1. Reagents and condition : (i) EtO₂CCl, Et₃N, THF, 0°, then excess CH₂N₂, ether, 0°, (ii) PhSH, cat. Rh₂(OAc)₄, CH₂Cl₂, RT, (iii) NaBH₄, MeOH, -20°.

Experimental

(*S*)-3-(*N,N*-Dibenzylamino)-1-thiophenylbutan-2-one (**5**) : Ethyl chloroformate (0.47 g, 4.4 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *N,N*-dibenzylalanine (1.0 g, 3.7 mmol) and Et₃N (0.44 g, 4.4 mmol) in THF (10 ml) at 0°. After 30 min, the precipitate formed was filtered and the filtrate was added dropwise to a freshly prepared solution of CH₂N₂ (prepared from 1.52 g, 14.8 mmol nitrosomethyl urea and 1.82 g KOH in 20 ml ether) over 1 h at 0°. The reaction mixture was then allowed to warm to room temperature for 3–4 h. It was washed with satd. NaHCO₃ solution, dried and evaporated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by silica gel chromatography (10% EtOAc in pet. ether) to give **5** (0.70 g, 64%), m.p. 94–95° (EtOAc-pet. ether) (Found : C, 73.7; H, 6.45; N, 14.32. C₁₈H₁₉N₃O

†Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on his 75th birthday.

requires : C, 73.72; H, 6.48; N, 14.33%); $[\alpha]_D^{27} -144.54$ (*c*, 1.1, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1620, 2100, 2800, 3130 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 1.29 (3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH₃), 3.39 (1H, m, CH-N), 3.51 (2H, d, *J* 13.5 Hz, CH₂Ph), 3.77 (2H, d, *J* 13.5 Hz, CH₂Ph), 5.96 (1H, s, CHN₂), 7.27–7.42 (10H, m, ArH).

(*S*)-3-(*N,N*-Dibenzylamino)-1-thiophenylbutan-2-one (**6**) : To a solution of thiophenol (0.26 g, 2.43 mmol) and Rh₂(AcO)₄ (0.002 g) in CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml) was added dropwise a solution of **5** (0.17 g, 0.6 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (3 ml) over 2 h. The reaction mixture was stirred for another 30 min, then diluted with ether (20 ml), washed with cold dil. NaOH solution (2×10 ml) and water (2×10 ml) and dried. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure, followed by silica gel chromatography (5% EtOAc in pet. ether) gave **6** (0.15 g, 70%) as an oil; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +8.0$ (*c*, 0.5, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 1670, 2920, 3020 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 1.04 (3H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH₃), 3.37 (2H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz, CH₂Ph), 3.56 (1H, q, *J* 6.9 Hz, CH-N), 3.63 (2H, d, *J* 13.6 Hz, CH₂Ph), 3.77 (1H; d, *J* 15.2 Hz, CH₂SPh), 3.92 (1H, d, *J* 15.2 Hz, CH₂SPh), 7.09–7.27 (15H, m, ArH).

(2*R*,3*S*)-3-(*N,N*-Dibenzylamino)-1-thiophenylbutan-2-ol (**7**) : NaBH₄ (0.02 g, 0.48 mmol) was added to a solution of **6** (0.15 g, 0.4 mmol) in MeOH (3 ml) at –20°. After 30 min, the reaction was quenched with a drop of HOAc and diluted with ether (15 ml). The mixture was washed with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was purified by silica gel chromatography (10% EtOAc in pet. ether) to give **7** (0.09 g, 60%) as an oil (Found : C, 76.58; H, 7.20; N, 3.69. C₂₄H₂₇NOS requires : C, 76.39; H, 7.16; N, 3.71%); $[\alpha]_D^{25} -1.06$ (*c*, 1.5, CHCl₃); ν_{\max} (neat) 2920, 3020, 3400 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz) δ 1.04 (3H, d, *J* 6.7 Hz, CH₃), 2.74–2.82 (1H, m, CHN),

2.84 (1H, dd, *J* 7.2, 13.1 Hz, CH₂SPh), 3.13 (1H, dd, *J* 2.9, 13.1 Hz, CH₂SPh), 3.32 (2H, d, *J* 13.3 Hz, CH₂Ph), 3.72 (1H, ddd, *J* 2.9, 7.2, 9.4 Hz, CH-OH), 3.82 (2H, d, *J* 13.3 Hz, CH₂Ph), 7.14–7.34 (15H, m, ArH).

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